

COLLECTION DEVELOPMENT POLICIES AND PROCEDURES IN THE PUBLIC LIBRARIES OF KHYBER PAKHTUNKHWA, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

The main objective of this study was to investigate the policies and procedures of collection development and their goals in the public libraries of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP). Based on the literature review a questionnaire survey was designed to achieve the objectives of the study. Data was collected from all (N=18) public libraries of KP with 100% response rate. The collected data was analyzed with the help of SPSS, version 20. Analysis of the data reveals that there is a complete absence of formal collection development policies (CDPs) in the Public libraries of KP. In the absence of formal written CDPs libraries adopt variety of traditional strategies for collection development to fulfil users' need. The study suggests to the information professionals of the public libraries of KP to develop CDPs in consultation with the authorities to provide clarity and consistency in their collection development strategies and procedures.

Keywords: Collection Development Policies, Collection Development Procedures, Collection Development, Public Libraries

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INTRODUCTION

Collection Development Policies (CDPs) serve as blueprints for the operations of libraries through which they carry out their central tasks of acquiring, organizing, and managing library materials (Gregory, 2019). Collection development policies have proven valuable for many collection development and management librarians (Van Zijl, 2005). Collection development policies typically set up general framework for establishing the library's collection goals, in terms of both new acquisition and the maintenance of the existing items. Collection development policies help to ensure consistency in procedures and are also important in achieving appropriate balance in a library's collection (Gregory, 2019).

Public libraries are democratic institutions that acquire and disseminate information, create awareness and promote education among the people of the society irrespective of creed, race, gender, age and ethnic group (Warraich & Tahira, 2025). A major indicator of a good public library is the quality and quantity of its collections through which they achieve their goals to preserve human culture, values, knowledge and social customs (Kaliya & Baskaran, 2010). Collection development is continuous process therefore in absence of formal written CDPs public libraries might have been following certain procedures.

Public libraries collection in Pakistan is facing various problems and issues. These include lack of fund, poor number of local publications to meet educational needs, insufficient number of reputed book sellers in the country, problem of exchange rate, attempts by booksellers to supply old books at new prices, and high cost of reading materials. These issues highlight the need and importance of CDPs in the public libraries of Pakistan. The basic aim of the study in hand is to study to examine collection development policies and procedure followed for collection development and management and their goals in the public libraries of Pakistan the scope of which is limited to the province of KP.

Objectives of the Study

1. To examine whether public libraries in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa have predetermined collection development policies or follow general procedures for collection development.
2. To study the goals of collection development policies and procedures in the public libraries of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

Research Questions

1. Do public libraries in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa have predetermined collection development policies or follow general procedures for collection development and management?
2. What are the goals of collection development policies and procedures in the public libraries of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan?

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Collection development policy is a formal written statement of the principles guiding a library's selection of materials, including the criteria used in making selection and de-selection decisions (fields covered; degrees of specialization; levels of difficulty; languages; formats; balance, etc.) and policies concerning gifts and exchange (Reitz, 2022). An unambiguously worded CDPs can be very helpful in responding to challenges from pressure groups i.e. users of the community. Kennedy (2006) states that written CDPs are intended to govern the activities of a library in regard to its collection. Johnson (2014) narrates that CDPs provide guidelines within which the library selects and manages its collection. These guidelines are a contract between the library and its community, supplying a framework within which complex decisions are made with consistency and

reason. Vickery, (2004) has based his arguments on the of definition American Library Association which states that the “scope and nature of a library’s existing collections and the policies and plane for continuing development of resources, with precise designation of present collection strengths and current collecting intensity in relevant subject fields and a statement of selection philosophy as related to institutional goals, general selection criteria and intellectual freedom”. According to Fourie, (2001) CDPs provides planning and implementation guidelines for most collection building tasks. He further states that CDPs contain three kinds of statements

- A statement of objective which has direct bearing on the institution’s mission and philosophy
- A statement of principles which must be flexible enough to cover different situations that might arise
- A statement of implementation including staff procedures to ensure stability in decision making.

Van Zijl, (2005) considers it a document drawn up by a specific library to provide guidelines whereby the collection is developed and managed to meet the need of that particular user group. This policy should explain the past, present and future acquisition and collection management practices of the library for the edification of bibliographers, other library staff users, sponsors and anyone else who has an interest in the library in question. Therefore according to Harte, (2006) the key elements of a collection development policy appear to be that:

- It is a formal document
- It articulate the history, current practices and future goals of the collection
- It states principles governing a wide range of collection management activities

Purpose of Collection Development Policy

Given the lack of an agreed definition, it is informative to also consider the purpose of written CDPs. However, according to Harte, (2006) the precise purpose will vary according to the characteristics of the library in question. The review of the relevant literature shows that the primary purpose of written CDPs is to lay down guidelines for selecting materials for the collection of the library. It also describes steps on weeding (de-selection), retention, preservation and archiving. It helps in identifying gaps in collections and providing orientation to new staff. It can help the library users what to expect from the library and what to recommend to be added to the collection. According to Hoffmann and Wood, (2005) CDPs statement often focuses on the communication function: internally, with the users, staff, and administrators, and externally, with other libraries and institutions. Communication embraces a wide range of operations, including training, budgeting cooperative acquisitions, interaction with users, and shared services. The collection development plan is like business plan for a small business (Cassell & Futas, 1991). It is like a road map which outlines the steps to be taken to accomplish the goals of the business. Lorenzen, (2009) is of the opinion that the CDPs act as a planning tool, guide to selectors, ensures consistency and defence for challenges. Davidson and Dorner (2009) investigated that basic purpose of CDPs in public libraries is to ensure effective collection development and management. CDPs guide the collection development and provide a rational for its utility in public libraries.

Kelly (2015) notes that CDPs in public libraries must tend to focus on local topics, local contents and content creators, and the needs of local people. Fourie, (2001) also noted that CDPs are good communication tools both internally and externally. Internally CDPs

indicate to the parent organization the selection of certain materials in specific subject areas as matter of policy and externally it works as a policy document to communicate with the outside organizations or enter into a network or consortium. Therefore, there are several advantages of having CDPs in public libraries. Van Zijl (2005) strongly advocates using CDPs as a mean of protection which empowers library staff to provide them a framework to take informed and more consistent decisions.

Majority of the scholars and researchers favour written CDPs (Johnson, 2014; Gregory, 2019) however, Van Zijl (2005) and Snow (1996) indicated problems surrounding the use of CDPs in public libraries. Snow states that CDPs are theoretical and intellectual guides to selection rather than practical one. Moreover, CDPs are inflexible and unresponsive to change. If the policy is not constantly revised, it loses any value it might have had which is again a difficult job. Similarly, Gregory (2019) also noted that in addition to print materials there has been a rapid infusion of electronic resources. This infusion has strained the rules and guidelines typically found in current CDPs related to printed materials. To give room for the electronic resources libraries must re-examine their CDPs and update them to reflect the addition of concerns specific to the electronic format.

There is general consensus among the authors (Van Zijl, 2005; Johnson, 2014; Fourie, 2001; and Atkinson, 2011) in what should be included in a collection development policy. Gregory (2011) defined a good CDP as the expression of collection management, stating that a good CDP informed library staff and users about the mission statement of the library, selection zones, and requirements, selection tools, strong and weak areas of the collection, shared resources policy and capacity, utilization of available funds and budget, as well as the policies and possibilities of accepting donations and gifts or exchanging library materials, exchange of digital resources and employee training initiatives.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Keeping in view the objectives of the study a questionnaire was used to collect data from public libraries of KP. The study covers all public libraries in KP as mentioned in Table 1 (<https://hed.gkp.pk/content/libraries>)

Table 1: *List of public libraries in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa*

Name of Public Library	District
Shuhada-e-Army Public School Public library Peshawar	Peshawar
Rahman Baba Public Library Peshawar	Peshawar
Charsadda Public Library, Charsadda	Charsadda
Mardan Public Library	Mardan
Buneer Public Library, Buneer	Buneer
Fazal Haqkani Public Library Swabi	Swabi
Khushal Khan Khattak Memorial Library, Akora Khattak	Nowshera
Swat Public Library, Mingora Swat	Mingora
Timergara Public Library, Lower Dir	Lower Dir
Chitral Public Library, Chitral	Chitral
Hakim Abul Salam Public Library Haripur	Haripur
Ghazi Public Library Gazi, Haripur	Haripur
Jalal Baba Public Library, Abbottabad	Abbottabad
Mansehra Public Library, Manshera	Manshera
Kohat Public Library, Kohat	Kohat
Bannu Public Library	Bannu
Lakki Marwat Public Library, Lakki Marwat	Lakki Marwat

Mufti Mehmood Public Library, D.I.Khan,

Dera Ismail Khan

Analyses of the data were made with the help of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. The response rate was 100%.

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Collection Development Policies

The literature depicts that collection development and management policies help serve as a blueprint for the operations of libraries. Collection development and management policies inform the administrators, library professionals, teaching and students communities about the role of library in supporting the institutional missions and objectives. Most importantly it provides a course of action to the librarians and guides the process of selection, acquisition, funds allocation for various subjects/heads, and weeding.

Looking to the importance of CDPs, library professionals were asked to provide information about their CDPs. Libraries with formal written CDPs were also requested to provide a copy of the same. Data in table 2 indicate that majority (77%) of the public libraries do not have formal written CDPs. Written CDPs were only available in 4 public libraries. Since collection development is continues process therefore in absence of formal written CDPs public libraries might have been following certain procedures.

It was observed that in the absence of formal written CDPs, most public libraries have some type of documents containing independent random procedures for selection, acquisition, and other library activities.

Table 2: Presence of Formal Written Policy for Collection Development and Management in the Public Libraries (N=18)

Statements	Frequency	Percentage
Library have formal written policy for collection development & management	4	22%
Library have no formal written policy for collection development & management	14	77%

Goals of Collection Development Policies and Procedures

Collection development and management are the two most important programs of any public library, driven by goals and objectives. The goals of collection development are multiple; materials are easily accessible and ensure their availability to the users. It rationally develops collection in response to the needs within the existing financial resources. Collection development and management of public libraries is to support the institution's mission and objectives, promote reading habits in society, preserve materials for future generations, and to maximise the accessibility of information to the users in an individual as well as collective capacity by entering into consortia programs. In the modern era it aims to develop and maintain a balanced CM program in the light of increasing electronic resources as well.

To know about the goals, aims and objectives of the existing policies and procedures of the public libraries of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, thirteen points were provided to the library professionals' mention the functions of their collection development policies and procedures.

The study found diverse goals of collection development and management policies and procedures in the public libraries of KP. The primary goals included supporting institution's mission and objectives, enhance general literacy in the community, promote education by making materials accessible ensuring their availability in the public libraries. To preserve cultural materials for present and future users and promote local language and

culture was also among the prime objectives. In order to make use of existing financial resources and anticipate user needs CDPs policies and procedures guide library professionals in the public libraries of the province (table 3).

Table 3: Goals of Collection Development and Management Policies and Procedure of a Public Libraries (N=18)

Goals of policies and procedures for CM	Frequency	Percentage
To support the institution's mission and objectives	18	100%
To enhance general literacy in the community	18	100%
To preserve and promote local language and culture	13	72%
To promote research culture among regional, national, and international readers & researchers	13	72%
To promote the educational role of the institution	15	83%
To make material accessible	18	100%
To preserve the material for present users and users to come (in the future)	15	83%
To provide material by ensuring its availability to users	18	100%
To rationally develop collections in response to user's needs	14	77%
To make the best use of existing financial resources	14	77%
To make informed decisions in terms of format choices	8	44%
To develop and maintain a balanced collection management program in light of increasing electronic resources	6	33%
To maximize the availability of special resources by entering and maintaining collaborative programs	5	27%

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study found an absence of CDPs in most of the public libraries of KP. It was noted that in the absence of formal CDPs public libraries in the province follow general procedures for collection development to fulfil the needs of users. Majority of the public libraries in KP do not have formal CDPs yet the libraries with the claims of having CDPs were found with written instructions and directional guidelines for procurement of library material in line with the public library procedures.

These libraries are having goals for collection development and management to "support the institution's mission and objectives", "enhance general literacy in the community", "make material accessible", "provide material by ensuring its availability to users", and "rationally develop collections in response to user's needs".

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